

New data on the geochemical and mineralogical features of the main manganese- and iron-bearing ore occurrences in the Central Srednogie Zone, Bulgaria

Silvia Chavdarova, Milen Stavrev, Atanas Hikov, Irena Peytcheva

Geological Institute, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Acad. G. Bonchev Str., Bl. 24, 1113 Sofia, Bulgaria;
e-mails: silvia.chavdarova@gmail.com (corresponding author); m.b.stavrev@gmail.com;
ahikov@geology.bas.bg; irena.peytcheva@erdw.ethz.ch

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Abstract. The main goal of the present study is the characterization of the mineralogical and geochemical features of polymetallic (Mn- and Fe-bearing) nodules, lens- and layer-like bodies from different localities in the central part of the Late Cretaceous Srednogie metallogenic zone, Bulgaria. The research is based on field studies, sampling and optical microscopy, followed by a combination of analytical techniques: XRD, SEM-EDS, ICP-OES and LA-ICP-MS methods. They define pyrolusite as the main ore mineral of the studied occurrences, while manganite, todorokite, bixbyite, sarkinite, hematite and hauerite are rarer. The most common gangue minerals are quartz, calcite and zeolites. Based on the MnO/SiO₂ ratio, the established minerals are divided into two groups: manganese (i) and silica-manganese (ii) phases, respectively. Their trace element composition is dominated by a high content of V, Zn, Mo, W, Co, Ni, Cu, As, Tl and Sr, whereas some of them belong to the group of the critical raw materials for high-tech products. The measured values for Y and rare earth elements of the studied oxides and hydroxides are low compared to their concentrations in modern polymetallic nodules of the Pacific Ocean. Chondrite-normalized patterns indicated weak LREE enrichment with respect to MREEs and HREEs, which are slightly depleted. Common weak to strong negative Ce anomaly, accompanied by various Sm and Eu anomalies, is also observed. The close proximity of the Late Cretaceous volcanic rocks to the Mn- and Fe-bearing ore mineralization and some structural and textural features of the studied minerals suggest hydrothermal origin of the main Mn-Fe ore occurrences in the Panagyurishte area.

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INTRODUCTION

On the territory of Bulgaria, the complex Alpine tectono-magmatic and metamorphic evolution is accompanied with and/or followed by local processes of sedimentation. Diverse ore deposits and occurrences are related to these complex geological processes. In the Srednogie metallogenic zone, the

main occurrences are represented by Late Cretaceous porphyry-copper (Elatsite, Assarel, Medet, Vlaykov Vrah) and epithermal Au-Cu deposits (*e.g.*, Chelopech, Elshitsa; Popov *et al.*, 2002, Kouzmanov *et al.*, 2009; Gallhofer *et al.*, 2015). During the Paleogene and Neogene, the tectono-magmatic and related sedimentary processes shifted to the south and west in the Rhodope-Serbo-Macedonian Massif with the forma-

tion of the Paleogene and Neogene polymetallic vein and skarn-hosted deposits (Laki, Madan, Thermes, Olympias-Stratoni Chalkidiki), intrusion-related gold and Mo-W (Kavala, Pangeon, Kimmeria, Babyak), intermediate- to high-sulfidation epithermal gold (e.g., Spahievo, Madzharovo, Perama Hill), detachment-related sedimentary rock-hosted gold at Ada Tepe (Kesebir-Kardamos dome), and porphyry Cu-Au(-Mo) (e.g., Skouries, Maronia; Melfos and Voudouris, 2012, 2017; Voudouris *et al.*, 2016; Popov and Popov, 2019; Stavrev *et al.*, 2021, and references therein). Bigger manganese deposits (Obrochishte, Black Sea basin; Dekov *et al.*, 2020) and smaller Fe-Mn bearing occurrences (Dimitrov and Kostov, 1954) are also known to be related to the Alpine orogeny. The latter are the focus of the present study, as modern polymetallic Fe-Mn nodules, crusts and sediments of the Pacific Ocean are also sources of Ni, Co, Cu, rare earth elements (REEs) and yttrium (Hein *et al.*, 2013; Stoyanova *et al.*, 2021), and we would like to re-estimate the potential of ancient manganese occurrences for strategic metals.

The increasing needs of society for metals suggest the use of modern techniques for exploration and characterization of mineral raw materials as a source of high-tech products. In this context, our interest is focused on the clarification of the major and trace element composition of manganese- and iron-bearing ore occurrences situated at the contact zones between volcanics and the overlying clayey-carbonate sediments in the central parts of the Srednogorie Zone (Fig. 1). This main fertile metallogenic region in Bulgaria is part of the extensive Late Cretaceous Apuseni-Banat-Timok-Srednogorie (ABTS) belt (e.g., Popov *et al.*, 2002; von Quadt *et al.*, 2005; Gallhofer *et al.*, 2015).

Herein, we present new field, mineralogical and geochemical data on the main manganese (\pm Fe) ore occurrences in the Panagyurishte ore region (Toplika, Momin Skok and Dalgi Rid) that were investigated earlier by Dimitrov and Kostov (1954). The study is focused on the distribution of some ore and critical elements such as Mn, Ni, Co, V, Mo, REEs, Y, Sc, W, Sr, etc., whose use is constantly growing in modern high- and green-tech technologies (Hein *et al.*, 2013). Our motivation for this work is related to the opportunity to shed light on the most perspective locations of nodules and nodule-like bodies with regard to different economically important elements in the area. Combining the field and basic laboratory methods with modern SEM-EDS and LA-ICP-MS methods, we also wish to contribute to a better understanding of the geological environment and the ore formation processes during Late Cretaceous times.

GEOLOGICAL SETTING

The studied manganese (\pm Fe) ore occurrences Toplika, Momin Skok and Dalgi Rid are situated in the Central Srednogorie Zone, close to the town of Panagyurishte and about 90 km to SE of Sofia. In the range of the Srednogorie metallogenic zone, the ore occurrences are considered part of the Panagyurishte ore region, which is the most important source of metals, such as copper and gold, in the country (Popov *et al.*, 2012). The geology of the district is represented mainly by Upper Cretaceous volcanics and their sedimentary cover, as well as younger sediments (Fig. 1).

The volcanics and volcano-sedimentary rocks in the area belong to the Chelopech Formation (Moev and Antonov, 1978). It includes andesites to trachyandesites and their agglomerate to ash tuffs. Locally, acid dacite-rhyodacite and rarer rhyolitic igneous varieties are also developed. In the upper levels, the magmatic rocks of the unit are intercalated and covered by marlstones, argillites and clayey limestones. Based on paleontological microfauna finds, the age of the formation is determined as Coniacian-Santonian (e.g., Dimitrova *et al.*, 1984). The lower boundary of this rock sequence with the variegated metamorphic basement is transgressive. Above the Chelopech Formation, with an unclear contact, lies the Mirkovo Formation (Moev and Antonov, 1978). It is comprised of reddish to light pinkish clayey limestones interbedded with marlstones dated as late Santonian-Campanian (e.g., Karagjuleva *et al.*, 1974). Silica-manganese nodules were observed and described close to the contact zone with the volcanics of the Chelopech Formation (e.g., Kostov, 1945; Dimitrov and Kostov, 1954, Chavdarova *et al.*, 2021). The Mirkovo Formation is overlain, with a normal lithological boundary, by the sediments of the Chugovitsa Formation (Moev and Antonov, 1978). Its composition includes predominantly interbedding of marlstones, clayey limestones and calcareous sandstones with widespread tuffs and tuffaceous sandstones in the basal levels. Based on microfossil remains (Vrãbljanski *et al.*, 1961; Dimitrova *et al.*, 1984), the age of the Chugovitsa Formation is defined as Campanian-Maastrichtian.

FIELD OBSERVATIONS, SAMPLING AND ANALYTICAL METHODS

During the field activities related to the present study, all three main manganese- and iron-bearing ore occurrences (Toplika, Momin Skok and Dalgi

Fig. 1. Simplified geological map of part of the Panagyurishte ore region (modified from Iliev and Katskov, 1990; see also Katskov and Iliev, 1993). The inset shows the position of the studied region on the tectonic map of Bulgaria (after Ivanov, 2017).

Rid) in the Central Srednogorie Zone, Bulgaria, were studied to reevaluate their present-day status. Established ore occurrences are represented by a single or numerous accumulations of silica and manganese (\pm Fe) oxides and hydroxides formed mostly as small lens-like, nest-like and layer-like bodies. An exception is the bigger (about 25 \times 5 m) lenticular silicified body cemented by ore minerals in the Toplika area.

Over 40 samples of silica-manganese nodules and nodule-like bodies at the contact zones between the clayey calcareous sediments and the volcanic rocks were collected. The mineral relationships and associations were studied in thin and polished sections under a microscope. The major element composition in the samples was obtained by SEM-EDS, using the JEOL JSM-6610LV equipment at the University of Belgrade, Serbia. Trace elements in the same samples were measured by LA-ICP-MS (PerkinElmer ELAN DRC-e ICP-MS attached to a New Wave UP193FX LA system) at the Geological Institute, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences. To determine the major elements in whole-rock samples, the Varian Vista-MPX CCD Simultaneous ICP-OES system of the certified laboratory “Aquateratest”, Sofia, was used. The mineral composition was also

defined by X-Ray diffraction (XRD), using both PANalytical Empyrean instrument at the Institute of Physical Chemistry, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, and Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer at the X-Ray Structural Analysis Laboratory at the Faculty of Geology and Geography, Sofia University.

MORPHOLOGY, MINERALOGICAL FEATURES AND GEOCHEMISTRY OF THE MANGANESE- AND IRON-BEARING ORE BODIES

Toplika ore occurrence

The ore occurrence in the Toplika area is situated about 4 km NE of the village of Popintsi, on the right bank of the Strelchanska Luda Yana River. The established ore mineralization is revealed as one large lenticular to irregular silicified body impregnated with ore minerals. It has a length of about 25 m in E–W direction and is about 5 m wide in N–S direction, respectively (Fig. 2a, b). The ore body marks the brittle rough contact zone between the materials of the Chelopech and Mirkovo formations, represented here by weakly weathered andesites (mixed with tuffs) and pink-reddish clayey limestones. Single nodules consisting of silica to silica-manganese

Fig. 2. Field photographs of outcrops from the Toplika ore occurrence: main outcrop (a), represented by brecciated quartz with typical ore cementation (b). Outcrop of reddish clayey limestones (e), including thin layer-like ore-bearing interbeds (d, e, f) and silica (e, g) to manganese-silica (c) nodules cross-cut by late chalcedony veinlets.

and/or iron-bearing phases or separate layers (up to 15 cm thick) are less abundant (Fig. 2c–f). Locally, among the reddish clayey limestones, rare flint lenticular nodules were observed (Fig. 2e, g). Often, the ore nodules and bodies are crossed by late quartz-chalcedony veinlets (Fig. 2c, e, g).

The ore mineralization is represented mainly by Mn (\pm Fe, Si, Ba) oxides and hydroxides. This is reflected in the whole-rock composition (Table 1),

showing contents of MnO up to \sim 10 wt%, SiO₂ between 81–94 wt% and FeO_t between 2.5–4 wt%. In the main ore body, the mineralization appears mainly as cementing brecciated quartz fragments, and resembles hydrothermal breccia. There are also many spheroidal aggregates with colloform texture composed of either entirely manganese (\pm Fe) minerals or those with alternating manganese and silica-manganese phases (Fig. 3a–d).

Fig. 3. BSE images demonstrating distinctive relationships between widespread Mn (\pm Fe) oxy-hydroxides and gangue minerals in different samples from the Panagyurishte district: a–d) spherulitic to colloform textures and massive aggregates of manganese oxides, hydroxides and gangue minerals from the Toplika ore occurrence; e–g) Colloform texture, single semi-rounded grains and massive to needle-shaped oxy-hydroxide aggregates, some of them locally cementing gangue mineral phases from the Momin Skok ore occurrence; h) Massive to elongated and flattened ore minerals associated with silicates from the Dalgi Rid ore occurrence. The major element content (oxides, wt.%) of the individual analyses is shown.

Table 1
Whole-rock chemical composition (wt%) of representative samples from the Mn-bearing (\pm Fe) ore occurrences in the Panagyurishte area

Ore occurrence	Toplika		Momin Skok			Dalgi Rid			
Sample №	Tpl-2a	Tpl-5	Ms-1	Ms-1a	Ms-2a	DR-4-1	DR-5	DR-7	DR-10
Al ₂ O ₃	0.40	0.24	0.69	0.61	1.39	0.49	1.05	0.61	1.46
BaO	0.69	0.08	6.09	1.40	4.16	0.12	0.26	0.09	0.40
CaO	0.53	0.15	1.08	0.47	1.61	0.89	19.51	0.75	8.72
Fe ₂ O _{3t}	3.91	2.45	5.44	4.93	10.53	6.54	2.47	4.65	4.70
K ₂ O	0.29	0.21	1.05	0.28	1.25	0.12	0.19	0.20	0.32
MgO	0.30	0.23	0.52	0.47	1.27	0.26	0.83	0.25	0.48
MnO	9.67	1.26	64.72	10.32	54.25	18.23	50.73	15.29	12.57
Na ₂ O	0.06	0.09	0.14	0.12	0.32	0.08	0.09	0.08	0.09
P ₂ O ₅	<0.05	<0.05	0.13	<0.05	0.09	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05
SO ₃	<0.05	0.25	0.62	0.19	0.49	<0.05	0.65	<0.05	0.53
SiO ₂	80.74	93.65	5.02	53.32	9.79	71.83	2.37	76.59	61.95
SrO	0.06	0.03	1.38	0.08	1.01	<0.01	0.04	<0.01	0.04
TiO ₂	0.09	<0.01	0.07	0.09	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.04
LOI (H ₂ O ⁺)	3.09	1.08	12.83	28.12	13.08	1.06	21.61	1.17	8.64
H ₂ O ⁻	0.52	0.28	1.20	0.70	2.23	0.16	0.66	0.25	0.37
Total	100.35	100.00	100.98	101.10	101.49	99.81	100.50	99.97	100.31

Note: Fe₂O_{3t} – Total content of FeO and Fe₂O₃; LOI (H₂O⁺) – Loss on ignition; H₂O⁻ – Non-bonded water (moisture released during drying of the crushed samples).

The main identified ore mineral is pyrolusite, while todorokite, sarkinite, hematite and hauerite have limited distribution (representative XRD spectra in Fig. 4). The most common gangue miner-

als are quartz (\pm chalcedony), calcite and zeolites. Based on the ratio of the major oxides (MnO and SiO₂), the established ore minerals are divided into two groups: manganese (i) and silica-manga-

Fig. 4. X-ray powder diffraction analyses of Mn-Fe-bearing samples at the Toplika ore occurrence.

Table 2

Representative SEM-EDS and LA-ICP-MS data for major and trace element composition of Mn (\pm Fe) oxides and hydroxides from the main ore occurrences in the Panagyurishte area

Ore occurrence	Toplika			Momin Skok				Dalgi Rid		
Sample №	Tpl-2a			MS-1a		MS-2a		DR-5		
Group	Mn		Si-Mn	Mn	Si-Mn	Mn	Si-Mn	Mn		Si-Mn
Major elements, wt%										
SiO ₂	0.49	0.96	72.83	1.79	2.34	0.97	4.81	0.84	0.65	13.03
Al ₂ O ₃	0.66	lod	lod	1.10	lod	0.55	1.29	0.83	1.11	2.56
FeO _t	2.00	3.38	lod	1.39	1.50	lod	4.44	1.30	lod	1.03
MnO	78.31	82.04	19.50	80.10	69.78	86.76	64.32	87.87	87.84	65.34
MgO	lod	lod	lod	lod	1.59	lod	0.73	lod	lod	0.67
CaO	lod	0.49	1.21	1.16	2.27	0.32	1.09	0.60	0.42	3.65
Na ₂ O	lod	lod	lod	lod	0.64	lod	lod	lod	lod	lod
K ₂ O	lod	lod	lod	lod	lod	lod	1.30	lod	lod	lod
Total	81.46	86.87	93.54	85.54	78.12	88.60	77.98	91.44	90.02	86.28
Trace elements, ppm										
V	327	500	170	133	76	66	86	100	<45.84	430
Co	48	47	147	5.2	47	<0.60	15	70	43	24
Ni	53	57	22	11	74	33	12	<80.86	110	29
Cu	821	461	159	316	246	810	162	222	225	898
Zn	187	282	146	126	103	196	213	<265.59	<241.94	117
Ga	47	33	8.8	41	10	48	35	36	48	23
Ge	4.9	<5.13	6.7	26	14	16	16	<85.70	<68.47	47
As	28	120	63	352	330	436	762	282	279	1642
Sr	619	3117	2544	2157	5039	417	12296	370	349	59
Y	11	13	7.6	24	25	6.2	24	9.4	11	68
Mo	192	393	154	102	277	109	498	51	155	40
Sb	9.5	8.0	0.96	5.3	21	506	25	<25.45	<13.42	8.3
Ba	26180	36041	26818	62157	79435	1450	70487	2292	2679	297
La	4.50	21.74	8.51	110.11	33.97	<0.16	12.12	10.99	8.94	65.74
Ce	5.36	0.57	2.30	3.39	1.00	<0.17	2.43	11.34	10.20	114.71
Pr	0.73	2.34	1.06	4.15	2.07	<0.19	1.18	2.56	<1.38	15.05
Nd	2.99	10.07	3.70	19.51	4.37	<0.86	5.76	13.79	<8.73	56.50
Sm	1.50	1.98	2.25	<1.35	<1.58	<0.74	<0.82	<8.44	<10.40	8.21
Eu	0.70	0.78	<0.52	0.65	0.79	<0.22	1.53	<1.27	<1.57	2.00
Gd	<1.32	1.30	1.56	2.93	4.56	<0.69	1.32	<4.32	<5.39	9.79
Tb	<0.13	0.18	0.19	<0.16	0.36	<0.09	0.23	<0.63	<0.79	1.26
Dy	<0.76	2.26	<1.00	1.15	1.72	<0.57	1.97	<2.60	<3.21	9.86
Ho	0.33	0.36	0.23	<0.18	0.61	<0.18	0.44	<0.65	<0.81	2.06
Er	<0.65	<1.14	<0.92	2.00	1.67	<0.71	1.49	<2.90	<3.59	6.97
Tm	<0.20	<0.19	<0.19	<0.33	<0.21	<0.13	0.18	<0.60	<0.75	0.89
Yb	<0.98	1.75	<1.50	1.76	<0.99	<0.60	1.37	<3.84	<4.76	5.10
Lu	<0.15	0.20	0.18	<0.27	0.28	<0.17	0.16	<0.63	<0.78	0.64
W	128	141	57	75	38	54	32	103	396	25
Tl	10	20	6.6	7.0	111	6.1	74	<29.46	<25.18	<1.19
Pb	3.4	3.0	<1.23	4.4	15	<0.42	8.8	40	72	131
U	11	5.9	2.3	7.3	2.5	6.4	4.5	3.3	3.2	4.9

Note: FeO_t – Total content of FeO and Fe₂O₃; lod – Limit of detection; Mn – Manganese group; Si-Mn – Silica-manganese group; Data for the content of TiO₂ and P₂O₃ are below the detection limit and not included.

nese (ii) phases (Chavdarova *et al.*, 2021; see also Table 2). In the first group (i), the composition of the major oxides varies as follows: MnO (47.15–82.04 wt%), FeO_i (1.08–6.27 wt%) and SiO₂ (up to 2.01 wt%). Typical trace elements (measured by LA-ICP-MS) in this group are: Co (3–87 ppm), Ni (46–309 ppm), Cu (221–1172 ppm), Sr (155–5725 ppm), V (277–691 ppm), Zn (187–508 ppm), Mo (134–581 ppm) and W (113–217 ppm). The second group (ii) includes minerals with higher values of SiO₂ (8.95–72.83 wt%) and lower contents of MnO (19.50–58.23 wt%) and FeO_i (up to 1.79 wt%). The trace element composition of the ore minerals in this group is dominated by more significant values for Co (21–259 ppm), Ni (15–66 ppm), Cu (72–253 ppm), Sr (318–6912 ppm), V (153–697 ppm), Zn 99–459 ppm), Mo (142–534 ppm) and W (56–173 ppm). Other oxides that were detected by EPMA analyses are Ba, Al, K, and Ca (BaO 1.25–2.59 wt%, Al₂O₃ 0.33–0.67 wt%, K₂O 0.23–0.40 wt% and CaO 0.17–1.21 wt%). Typical impurities with variable content from a limit of detection (lod) to measured values are Ga, Ge, As, Sb, Tl, Y, Pb and U. The REE concentration in the analyzed samples is very low. Only La and Ce differ in values, reaching up to 22 ppm. The chondrite-normalized REE diagrams display patterns with a relatively uneven

distribution of elements between the individual analyses in both of groups (Fig. 5a, d). Slight LREE (La to Nd) enrichment and slight MREE (Sm–Dy)/HREEs (Ho–Lu) depletion were observed. The most significant is predominantly strong negative Ce anomaly. The patterns are also distinguished, for example, by small negative Sm and small positive Eu anomalies, as well as with variations of the other REEs. There are significant differences between the REE distribution in ore minerals (Fig. 5a, d) and whole-rock samples from the Toplika ore occurrence (Fig. 6) compared to earlier data for volcanic rocks (von Quadt *et al.*, 2005; Kouzmanov *et al.*, 2009; Hikov, 2013) in the region.

The LA-ICP-MS trace element data for ore minerals from Toplika reveal significant positive correlations of Mn with Cu (0.88), Ga (0.97) and U (0.84); positive correlation with W (0.59) and Y (0.53); relatively positive correlations with Sb (0.45), Ge (0.43), Fe (0.46), Ni (0.40). Iron has strong correlations with Ni (0.97) and Sb (0.97) as well as relatively positive with Ge (0.48) and Cu (0.41). The more significant correlation coefficients between trace elements with higher contents are: V–Sr (0.77), V–Mo (0.91), As–Sr (0.87), As–Zn (0.78), As–Mo (0.94), Ni–Sb (0.98), Cu–Ga (0.91), Cu–U (0.92), Zn–Mo (0.78), Zn–W (0.72), Mo–Ba

Fig. 5. Chondrite-normalized REE distribution patterns of Mn (\pm Fe) ore minerals from the main ore occurrences in the Panagyurishte area: (a, d) Toplika; (b, d) Momin Skok; (c, d) Dalgi Rid. The REE composition of C1 chondrite is after Sun and McDonough (1989).

Fig. 6. Chondrite-normalized REEs distribution patterns of whole-rock samples from the Mn (\pm Fe) ore occurrences (Tpl, MS and DR data), and volcanic rocks (*a–c* of Literature data) in the Panagyurishte region. Published data for the volcanic rocks include: *a*) von Quadt *et al.* (2005); *b*) Kouzmanov *et al.* (2009); *c*) Hikov (2013). The REE composition of C1 chondrite is after Sun and McDonough (1989).

(0.74). Some of these elements show positive correlations with some of the major elements (*e.g.*, K, Ca, Na, P); with regard to REE composition, more high correlation values with LREEs followed by MREEs and lowest with HREEs are observed.

Momin Skok ore occurrence

This ore occurrence is located about 1 km SW of the village of Svoboda. The geological setting of the area is characterized by weathered andesites and their tuffs (Fig. 7*a*), as well as reddish marlstones of the Mirkovo Formation. At the contact between the volcanics and the sediment rocks, a variety of ore fragments are revealed. In some places, the ore mineralization is in the form of separated small rounded to irregularly shaped pieces (Fig. 7*b, d*) or as thin layers to lenticular bodies (Fig. 7*c, e, f*) among larger rock fragments.

Fig. 7. *a*) Panoramic view of the volcanic rocks outcropped close to the Momin Skok ore occurrence; *b, d*) individual Mn- and Fe-containing ore specimens; ore-bearing layers (*c, f*) and nests (*e*) included in the host sediment rocks.

The ICP-OES results for the samples from the Momin Skok ore occurrence (Table 1) show variations of the major oxides: MnO between 10–65 wt%, SiO₂ between 5–53 wt%, FeO_t between 5–11 wt% and BaO up to ~6 wt%.

According to the data obtained from X-ray diffraction analysis (Fig. 8), the following ore minerals are identified: pyrolusite, manganite, coronadite, goethite, bermanite and marcasite. The associated gangue minerals include quartz, periclase, calcite

and khademite. The microscopic observations and BSE images show similar mineral relationships to these from the Toplika ore occurrence. Here, we observed massive to needle-shaped oxy-hydroxide aggregates, some of which have colloform texture (Fig. 3e–g).

Based on the presence of the main elements Mn and Si, similar to the Toplika ore occurrence, the ore phases can be subdivided into two groups: manganese (i) and silica-manganese (ii) minerals (Table 2).

Fig. 8. X-ray powder diffraction analyses of some mineral phases from the Momin Skok ore occurrence.

In the manganese group, the values of the major oxides vary as follows: MnO (65.33–90.58 wt%), FeO_t (up to 1.94 wt%) and SiO₂ (up to 3.48 wt%). The typical trace elements are: V (56–206 ppm), Cu (122–810 ppm), Sr (417–19951 ppm), Zn (84–245 ppm), Mo (46–819 ppm), Tl (2–1013 ppm) and As (237–1458 ppm). Other elements with lower contents are Co, Y, Ni, U, Ga, Ge and Pb, while the contents of Sb show wide variation, reaching up to 506 ppm. The REEs in ore minerals from the Momin Skok ore occurrence show very low concentrations. The values of La (up to 143 ppm), Ce (up to 85 ppm) and Nd (up to 30 ppm) are more distinctive. The silica-manganese group includes minerals with higher values of SiO₂ (4.81–45.33 wt%) and lower content of MnO (31.23–64.98 wt%) and FeO_t (up to 10.69 wt%). There is no obvious difference in trace element composition between the two groups. On the chondrite-normalized REE patterns (Fig. 5b, d), almost all samples have a very similar distribution to the one in the Toplika ore occurrence. Except for the strong negative Ce anomaly, the negative Sm and positive Eu anomalies are also slightly more pronounced. In addition, these REE data (Fig. 5b, d) match well with the diagrams for whole-rock samples from the Momin Skok ore occurrence (Fig. 6) and are different from the volcanic rocks (von Quadt *et al.*, 2005; Kouzmanov *et al.*, 2009; Hikov, 2013) in the area; only one sample (MS-1) is close to volcanic rocks but with negative Sm anomaly.

The LA-ICP-MS trace element results for ore minerals at Momin Skok show positive correlations of Mn with Ga (0.70), Cu (0.62) and Tl (0.61). Also, a relatively positive correlation with Sb (0.48) is observed. The more significant correlation coefficients are established for: Cu–Sb (0.85), Mo–Sr (0.88), W–Y (0.71) and W–Pb (0.90). There are no clear correlations between the values of the most specific measured trace elements in the ore occurrence with data for the major elements and REEs.

Dalgi Rid ore occurrence

Unlike the other ore occurrences in the Panagyurishte ore region, traces of mining activity are observed here. The contact zone between the Upper Cretaceous rocks of the Mirkovo and Chelopech formations is marked by an established old gallery (Fig. 9a, b). Herein, we revealed levels of both massive ore mineralization (Fig. 9c, g) and single pieces covered with many small nodules and coatings (Fig. 9d, e) concentrated mainly among the host rocks. In proximity to the gallery, within reddish marlstones, rare flint to silica-manganese nodules with alternat-

ing concentric layers have been formed, filled with quartz and chalcedony (Fig. 9f).

The ICP-OES data for the samples from this ore occurrence (Table 1) show higher contents of MnO between 12.6–51 wt%, SiO₂ up to ~77 wt%, FeO_t between 2.5–6.5 wt% and CaO up to ~20 wt%.

The results from the powder X-ray diffraction analysis (Fig. 10) and microscopic/SEM-BSE study also show diversity of ore minerals. These are pyrolusite, braunite, bixbyite, hematite, neltnerite and pyrite. The main oxy-hydroxides form predominantly massive to flattened and elongated crystals (Fig. 3h). The most common gangue phases are quartz, fluorite, barite and calcite.

The values of MnO vary between 65.34–90.24 wt% (Table 2). The contents of the other oxides do not exceed 1 wt%, except for those of SiO₂ (10.85–13.03 wt%), Al₂O₃ (1.59–2.56 wt%) and CaO (1.96–3.65 wt%) in two of the analyses that are considered as a part of the silica-manganese group. Trace elements with more specific contents are Cu (135–1261 ppm), Sr (10–433 ppm), Mo (40–243 ppm), W (25–396 ppm) and As (126–1642 ppm). Impurities with lower or highly variable concentration are V, Co, Y, Ga, Ge, Ni, Zn, Pb, Sb, Tl and U. The content of REEs in the same samples is low. Higher values are measured for La (up to 66 ppm), Ce (up to 115 ppm) and Nd (up to 57 ppm). The chondrite-normalized diagrams (Fig. 5c, d) show a slight difference in the REE patterns for the Dalgi Rid ore occurrence. There is no relative enrichment or depletion in different REEs in the analyzed ore minerals from the manganese group. Besides, minor negative Ce anomalies, as well as slightly positive Sm and slightly negative Eu anomalies, are also observed. In the silica-manganese group, a small depletion in LREEs to HREEs is noticeable. As with other ore occurrences, the REE patterns of minerals and whole-rock samples from the Dalgi Rid ore occurrence differ from analyses of volcanic rocks from the region (Fig. 6); only one sample (DR-10) has a similar pattern to the volcanic rocks.

The most significant correlation coefficient of Mn from the ore samples from Dalgi Rid is calculated for Sr (0.88), while correlations with Mo (0.59), W (0.48), Co (0.44), Zn (0.44) and Cu (0.43) are relatively positive. Iron shows a positive correlation with As (0.65), V (0.63), Ge (0.60) and relatively positive with Y (0.43). The following more significant correlation coefficients have been established for the most characteristic impurities in ore minerals: Sr–Mo (0.72), Mo–Ni (0.74), Mo–W (0.71), Zn–Ba (0.84), V–As (0.96), V–Y (0.85), V–Pb

Fig. 9. *a, b*) Outcrops of an old gallery from the Dalgi Rid ore occurrence; *c, g*) massive ore mineralization in different host rocks; *d, e*) numerous small ore nodules and coatings incorporated into the host reddish limestones; *f*) specimen of silica-manganese nodule.

(0.76). There are predominantly strong correlations of V and As (partly for Fe) with REEs.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results for the major and trace elements of the studied Mn- (\pm Fe) minerals in the ore occurrences from the Panagyurishte ore region (Table 2), we can assume that the accumulation of Mo, Cu, V, Sr, As, and W is favored by the crystal-chemical and structural features of this type of oxides and hydroxides. The presence of these elements generally reflects the ore-bearing potential of the whole ore region, *i.e.*, some of the largest Late Cretaceous Cu-porphyry (\pm Mo) and epithermal deposits are formed in the Central Srednogorie Zone. On the other hand, the higher content of Co, Ni, Zn and Tl may also reflect local characteristic features, in regard to the source and evolution of ore-bearing fluids and the local deposition conditions. As de-

scribed above, all three Mn (\pm Fe) ore occurrences are formed in a similar position in the contact zone between the volcanic materials of the Chelopech Formation and the overlying pink-reddish clayey limestones of the Mirkovo Formation. However, only in some places are the Mn- (\pm Fe) nodules and layers formed, and all of them are enriched in Mo, Cu, V, Sr, As, W, partly also Co, Ni, Zn and Tl (Table 1). Consequently, the sources of the major and trace elements in the studied ore occurrences should be considered similar and (at least partly) related to magmatic rocks, as they are not found further in the sedimentary succession.

As an important part of “critical raw materials”, the REEs in the samples from the present study were of particular interest. Opposite to the current polymetallic nodules in the Pacific Ocean, the measured concentrations of these trace elements are insignificant, except for individual analyses, where the values reach up to ~ 100 ppm for some LREEs, *e.g.*, La. The content of the other REEs most often

Fig. 10. Powder X-ray diffraction diagrams of various minerals from the Dalgi Rid ore occurrence.

is below the limit of detection or varies up to ~10–20 ppm. The lower REE content and distinct REE patterns, compared to the volcanic rocks from the Panagyurishte region, give evidence that the REEs are transported and accumulated in the nodules and Mn-Fe layers in a form that differs from the elements in high concentration. Furthermore, the processes of their accumulations differ substantially

from the complex modern deep-sea hydro- and diagenetic processes (mostly at or below the calcium carbonate compensation depth), where REEs- and yttrium-rich nodules form (*e.g.*, Hein *et al.*, 2013). The pronounced negative Ce anomaly suggests oxidizing environment during the deposition and diagenesis of the sediments, which is in agreement with the strongly oxidized reddish marlstones of

Mirkovo Formation and deposition of highly oxidized minerals such as pyrolusite and barite. The negative Ce anomaly shows some similarities with the modern deep-sea metalliferous sediments that contain polymetallic nodules (Dubinin, 2004; Hikov *et al.*, 2022).

The following correlation coefficients have been calculated for the major and trace elements in whole-rock samples from the studied ore occurrences: strong positive between Mn and Ga (1.00), Zn (0.98), Ni (0.91), Y (0.89), W (0.88), Tl (0.81), Sb (0.85), Mo (0.83), Sr (0.80) and positive with Co (0.64), As (0.69), Ba (0.79). Besides, Mn has strong correlations with most REEs. For Fe, more characteristic is a strong positive correlation with As (0.75), while the correlations with Sb (0.55), Tl (0.56), Ge (0.50) and Ba (0.50) are relatively positive. These correlations are very similar to those listed above for the individual ore occurrences. The relationship of manganese and iron with the other trace elements is explained by sorption mechanisms of formation (*e.g.*, Hein *et al.*, 2013). Such formation of Mn and Fe oxides/hydroxides is followed by the sorption of oppositely charged dissolved metal species ions on the charged surfaces of the oxide phases.

Our working hypothesis for the genesis of the Mn (\pm Fe) ore occurrences is in accordance with the one developed by Dimitrov and Kostov (1954). The latter considered the nodules at Toplika, Momin Skok and Dalgi Rid as initially gel-like masses, subsequently partially dehydrated during diagenesis. At the end of the lithification process, the nodules and nodule-like bodies reduced their volume, whereas concentric and irregular cracks were formed and consequently filled with chalcedony and quartz veinlets. The same authors discussed the link of ore-formation to hydrothermal processes. In the study area, evidence for hydrothermal origin of the nodules is represented mainly by the brecciated quartz body, cemented by Mn- and Fe-bearing ore mineralizations at the Toplika ore occurrence. The volcanic rocks in the close vicinity are an additional prerequisite to suggest a volcanic source of the ore components. Probably, the most suitable “traps” for

the Mn- and Fe-bearing fluids related to the latest stages of the Late Cretaceous volcanic activity in the area are controlled by the lithological boundaries between the rocks. The ore deposition in certain places might be controlled tectonically, *e.g.*, in syncline folds, slopes and deeper parts next to the volcanics.

The hydrothermal origin of the studied Late Cretaceous Mn-Fe bearing ore mineralizations distinguishes them from the hydro- and diagenetic formation of modern Fe-Mn metalliferous nodules, *e.g.*, from the Clarion-Clipperton Zone of the Pacific Ocean (Hein *et al.*, 2013; Dimitrova *et al.*, 2014; Dekov *et al.*, 2020; Baláž, 2021). However, they show some mineral and geochemical similarities with modern deep-sea polymetallic nodules and metalliferous sediments, revealing enrichment in Mn and Fe, as well as Cu, Co, Ni, Zn, Mo, W, Tl, Sr and Ba (Stoyanova *et al.*, 2021), and partly hydrogenetic-diagenetic precipitation of metals cannot be excluded.

Further studies on the Mn-Fe ore occurrences will aim to solve problems in the determination of mineral phases due to the similarities in their optical features and in the SEM-EDS spectral data. They will include quantitative mineralogical studies combining QEMSCAN analyses with high-resolution element mapping, and Raman spectroscopy. We plan to combine the present results with further geochemical data (using, *e.g.*, Sr and Nd isotopes) for a better definition of the fluid and metal sources, as well as constraining the conditions and mechanisms of formation. U-Pb dating (on zircons) of the volcanic rocks close to the Mn- and Fe-bearing occurrences is crucial to constrain the time interval when the ore mineralization was deposited.

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